

ABOUT THIS DOCUMENT: This template reflects the workflow carried on Live Reviews organized and hosted by PREreview. You are welcome to adapt it to your specific use settings and needs.

PREREVIEW REVIEW COMPOSITION DOCUMENT

This document contains instructions for Live Review discussion participants who have volunteered to compile the notes from the Live Review event held on **[DATE]** to guide them in the collaborative writing of the review.

We aim to publish the review on [PREreview.org](#) by **[DATE].**

ABOUT YOU

This compiling activity is for you IF:

- On **[DATE]**, you **actively** participated in the collaborative discussion of **this preprint [\[ADD DOI LINK\]](#) AND you have contributed notes and feedback via this collaborative review discussion notes [\[ADD LINK TO LIVE REVIEW COLLABORATIVE NOTES DOCUMENT\]](#).**
- You are happy to dedicate additional asynchronous time to compile the notes you contributed to taking during the call into a review report that will be published on [PREreview.org](#).

IMPORTANT: If you have not contributed with feedback during the call we ask that you DO NOT contribute to putting the review together, as an important prerequisite of gaining access to the opportunity of signing the review as a review author is that you actually contributed with feedback.

WHAT WE EXPECT OF YOU

- By **[DATE]**, please review this document and the listed [identity options](#)

- By **[DATE]**, please draft the summary paragraph and/or the list of the minor and major concerns with feedback as indicated in the email from facilitators and is further [explained below](#)
- By **[DATE]**, please read and make the final edits to the review

WHAT YOU CAN EXPECT OF US

- We will **help coordinate the asynchronous collaborative writing** of the preprint review in this document and make sure the narrative of the review is coherent and constructive.
- We will **publish the review on [PREreview.org](#)** respecting your choice of identity disclosure - we aim to publish the review no later than **[DATE]**.
- If you encounter any issues while creating ORCID and PREreview accounts, please email us at help@prereview.org.

PREREVIEW IDENTITY OPTIONS

When the time to publish this review on PREreview.org comes, you will receive an email from help@prereview.org, subject “Be listed as a PREreview author”, with text guiding you to follow a link to add yourself as a reviewer on this review. At that point, you’ll have **3 options on how you wish to be associated (or not) with the review**.

- 1. NO RECOGNITION (no action required)**
 - *You choose this option if you don’t want to have your real identity associated with the review and don’t want to register for an account online.*
 - *This means that there will be no way for you to prove that you were part of this effort and that you contributed to providing feedback to this preprint.*
- 2. PSEUDONYMITY (ORCID and PREreview account registration required¹)**
 - *You choose this option if you don’t want to have your real identity associated with the review but are comfortable with registering your name on [ORCID](#) and creating a PREreview account.*
 - *This means that if you have not already, **you will need to create an ORCID account and a PREreview account**. A PREreview account will give you access to*

¹ Learn more about how to make accounts on PREreview and ORCID in our [FAQ section below](#).

two names with which you can sign your reviews: one is your “PREreview Pseudonym” which is a preassigned and uneditable combination of an animal and a color (e.g., yellow penguin), and one is the name corresponding to your ORCID iD, here referred to as your “Public name”. If you choose this option, your Pseudonym will be displayed as one of the authors of the review, but only you² (if you don’t share your Pseudonym with anyone) will know your real identity.

3. OPTION 3: PUBLIC IDENTITY (ORCID and PREreview account registration required¹)

- *You choose this option if you are comfortable with creating an ORCID and PREreview account and you want to sign the review with your name so that it links to your scholarly record and you can get recognition for your contribution to this review.*
- *This means that as in option 2, **you will have to create one account on ORCID and a PREreview account.** We will then add your public name to the list of review authors for this review.*

PREPRINT REVIEW COMPOSITION

IMPORTANT: Respecting your choice of authorship identity we will add your names (or not) to the list of preprint review authors on the published version on PREreview.org. Text in blue contains instructions on how to collaboratively compose this review and text copied and pasted from the discussion document and will not be included in the final review. PLEASE DO NOT EDIT OR DELETE BLUE TEXT.

When you publish the review on PREreview.org, make sure to only copy and paste the review written in black font, leaving out the blue help text and notes from the discussion document.

----review to be copied and pasted on PREreview text box starts here [DON'T COPY BLUE TEXT]----

This review is the result of a virtual, collaborative live review discussion organized and hosted by PREreview and [INSERT NAME OF PARTNER ORG]. The discussion was joined by X people in

² PREreview staff can also access your identity in our database should a violation of [Code of Conduct](#) be reported. We will never share your PREreview Pseudonym with anyone, and it is not something we access unless there is a need to communicate with a preprint review author or to temporarily or permanently block their account.

total, including: **[ADD NUMBER OF AUTHORS, EDITORS, FACILITATORS ETC AS APPLICABLE]**.

The authors of this review have dedicated additional asynchronous time over the course of two weeks to help compose this final report using the notes from the Live Review. We thank all participants who contributed to the discussion and made it possible for us to provide feedback on this preprint.

Summary paragraph: Overview, take-home message, positive feedback

*Please use the group answers to **questions 1-6** given during the discussion and pasted below for reference to write the review's summary paragraph. Some folks may have also answered other questions that were optional. We invite you to check those out too to help draft the Summary paragraph.*

Relevant discussion notes copied and pasted below from the collaborative notes document to help guide the summary paragraph composition. **[PLEASE DON'T EDIT THESE NOTES.]**

Research question

-
-
-

Research approach

-
-
-

Research finding(s)

-
-
-

Research relevance

-
-
-

Summary:

[PLEASE USE THIS SPACE TO DRAFT A SUMMARY PARAGRAPH BY COMPILING THE NOTES ABOVE]

Evidence and Examples: Major and Minor Concerns + Constructive Feedback

*Next, we want to list our concerns dividing them into Major and Minor. To do that, please refer to the group answers to **questions 7-17** given during the discussion and pasted below.*

Ideally, we want to associate constructive, clear, and actionable feedback to each concern. If you are unsure about something, be honest and say you are unsure. Don't feel afraid to admit if you are not confident about your concerns, or if part of the work is out of your area of expertise.

Relevant discussion notes copied and pasted from the collaborative notes document **[DO NOT EDIT OR DELETE THE TEXT IN BLUE]**:

Concerns with techniques/analyses

-
-
-

Details for reproducibility of the study

-
-
-

Figures and tables

-
-
-

Limitations discussed

-
-
-

Ethics

-
-
-

Additional comments

-
-
-

BASED ON THE TEXT ABOVE AND ADDITIONAL FEEDBACK YOU MAY HAVE, PLEASE USE THE SPACE BELOW TO WRITE THE MAJOR (IF NOT ADDRESSED IT WILL COMPROMISE THE INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS) AND MINOR CONCERNS. PLEASE ADD, IF POSSIBLE, CONSTRUCTIVE AND CLEAR SUGGESTIONS ON HOW TO ADDRESS THE CONCERN

[...]

[A list of major and minor concerns + feedback/suggestions starts here]

List of major concerns and feedback:

-
-
-

List of minor concerns and feedback:

-
-
-

Overall Assessment

[...]

Concluding remarks

We thank the authors of the preprint for posting their work openly for feedback. We also thank all participants of the Live Review call for their time and for engaging in the lively discussion that generated this review.

----review to be copied and pasted on PREreview text box ends here----

Conflict of Interest

During the publication step on [PREreview.org](#), you'll be asked if you or anyone else who participated in the writing of the review has any Conflict of interest or Competing interests with the authors of the preprint reviewed as discussed in our [Code of Conduct](#).

[...]

FAQs REGARDING ORCID AND PREREVIEW

What is an ORCID iD?

An ORCID iD is a persistent identifier that is unique to you. It is meant to uniquely identify researchers to make sure scholarly output is associated with the right author. You can imagine, for example, that there are more people than just you with your name, so having a unique identifier can ensure that the right researcher is recognized for the work they published.

Do I have to be a researcher to register on ORCID?

No. While the ORCID iD is used to track contributions to the scholarly record so it only makes sense to have one if you want to contribute to it, anyone can create one. And within the scope of the open scholarship movement, it is to elevate preprint reviews to being recognized as scholarly contributions.

Here you can read more about ORCID's [mission](#) and [vision](#).

How do I register my ORCID iD?

Here is a [VIDEO ON HOW TO CREATE YOUR ORCID iD](#). Note that you have full control over what content may be associated with your scholarly record and who sees that content.

Also note that when you sign up to PREreview, we will import basic information you made publicly available on your ORCID profile to your PREreview profile—e.g., your name, your

biography, your list of publications, and your publicly shared email address(es). If this information is set to private, none of it will be imported to your PREreview profile.

How do I make a PREreview account?

Click on the Login button on the menu at the top-right of <https://prereview.org> and use your ORCID credentials to authenticate your profile. Once you're logged in, you can add details about yourself by editing your public profile by going to the [My details](#) tab on PREreview.org but all fields are optional. Learn more about editing your profile in this [video demo](#).

FURTHER RESOURCES

- Open Reviewers Toolkit - published on Zenodo under CC BY 4.0
 - [Bias Reflection Guide](#)
 - [Reviewer Guide](#)
 - [Review Assessment Rubric](#)
- On the [PREreview](#) resource page, you will find resources to
 - learn more about our project
 - how to write a review
 - start a preprint journal club
- On the [PLOS Reviewer Center](#) with resources on [how to write a constructive review](#) and much more.